

Exercise

Step n^o0: Play the game and send a
screenshot of a victory screen:

PT - <https://xreee.github.io/reset/>

ENC - <https://gamut.games>

Step n^o1: Download the project seen in
class:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.550](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5504644)
4644

Do the following changes:

01

Create
dummies for
the "atack"
class

02

Do the tests to
verify the
functions:
"rightAtack" and
"rightTool"

03

Test if the return of
the function
"checkIfWin" works
correctly

Challenge:

The logic of a function of one class is wrong, find and prove why using an unit test.